

IAM4NFDI Deliverable 1.5.int

Updated VO Concept

A case study on the implementation of advanced requirements for access management

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Introduction

This document is the second in a series of deliverables of the [IAM4NFDI] Project focusing on the management of Virtual Organisations (VOs) within the NFDI-AAI. Following on from [D1.4.int], which outlined the basics of rights and roles management as well as the technical and organisational framework conditions, this document addresses the implementation of fine-grained access management for specific resources, as it was implemented as a pilot for [PUNCH4NFDI].

Initial Requirements and chosen Approach

Many consortia, and the services they provide, require highly granular access controls. They need permissions that are defined at the level of individual files or compute resources. To meet these requirements, the [PUNCH4NFDI] consortium and their [Community AAI] operator have developed a solution for managing fine-grained access to files and various computing resources. This solution relies on tools that are already used by both the consortium and the WLCG community.

Pattern Scopes

The first component of this implementation is the introduction of pattern/parametric scopes into the OAuth 2 authorization server. Pattern scopes are a special kind of OAuth scope that

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consist of a static prefix followed by a dynamic part that typically identifies the target resource. For example, a pattern scope might look like this:

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storage.read:/home/user1/data.txt
```

Here, “storage.read” is the static prefix that indicates a request for read access, while “/home/user1/data.txt” is the dynamic component that specifies the exact file to be accessed. These pattern scopes are sent together with regular scopes during the token-request phase, alongside the usual scopes needed for user authentication.

Whether these pattern scopes are permitted depends on the relationship between the OAuth Provider (OP) and the Resource Provider (RP). It is up to the administrators of the Community AAI to decide whether to grant this permission to all connected resource providers or only to those that explicitly request it. Moreover, the OP determines which pattern scopes are supported by the Community AAI, usually in collaboration with the consortium and the RP to ensure the solution meets their needs.

Policy Engine

The second component involves integrating a policy engine that makes the final decision on each access request, based on predefined access rules and permissions. For now, the chosen engine is Open Policy Agent [OPA], a widely adopted solution for this purpose. To keep the system flexible and avoid vendor lock-in, the Community AAI does not connect directly to OPA; instead, an intermediary script is used. This script is invoked by the Community AAI, receives all required information about the request, forwards it to OPA, obtains the validation result, transforms it into the format expected by the Community AAI, and then either continues or aborts the authentication based on whether the requested permissions are granted.

The OPA component can be hosted either by the Community AAI itself or by the consortium. This decision is negotiated among the consortium members and the Community AAI operator. If OPA is hosted by the Community AAI, it can also be shared with other consortia. To enable fine-grained access control, two elements must be defined in OPA:

1. Policies – written in the [Rego] language, typically defined once at the start. These can be authored by the Community AAI operator or the consortium.
2. Data – a set of entries that specify the actual permissions needed to satisfy the policies. This data is maintained regularly whenever fine-grained permissions change. Updates are performed by the consortium and the resource owners, and the resulting data set is loaded onto the OPA instance.

Conclusion and Outlook

The solution, co-developed with the PUNCH4NFDI consortium, satisfies the need for file-level access permissions and fine-grained control over computing resources. The [NFDI4Immuno] consortium has already expressed interest in using file-level permissions. Helmholtz ID (based on Unity), the CAAI for PUNCH4NFDI & NFDI4Immuno, is going to implement OPA integration in the near future on the corresponding instance and take it into operation. This approach can also be leveraged to manage authorisation for services that

currently rely on VO (Virtual Organisation) functionalities provided by the Community AAI. Maintaining the “Data” section of OPA may be simpler for service operators than managing an entire VO.

Bibliography

[Community AAI] <https://doc.nfdi-aa.de/community-aa-software/>

[D1.4.int] Apweiler, S., Bonn, M., Hübner, D., Michels, T., Pempe, W. (2025). IAM4NFDI Deliverable 1.4 - Initial Concept for Rights and Roles Management. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17249586>

[IAM4NFDI] IAM4NFDI Project, <https://base4nfdi.de/projects/iam4nfdi>

[NFDI4Immuno] NFDI consortium, <https://www.nfdi4immuno.de>

[OPA] Open Policy Agent, <https://www.openpolicyagent.org>

[PUNCH4NFDI] NFDI consortium, <https://www.punch4nfdi.de>

[Rego] Policy Language for the Open Policy Agent, <https://www.openpolicyagent.org/docs/policy-language>